

Fabrication of Nanocomposite Adsorbent Based on Manganese Dioxide-loaded Zeolite for Enhanced Removal of Cadmium from Contaminated Waters and Soils

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Over the last few decades, the contamination of natural waters and soils with heavy metals has become a serious problem in terms of human health and impact on the environment. Cadmium is one of the most toxic elements to humans. Environmental releases of Cd from anthropogenic activities such as mining, smelting, production of pigments and cadmium-nickel batteries, and the use of phosphate fertilizers have severely affected water and soil quality and increased the risk of human exposure. Among the methods used to remove cadmium from sewage and contaminated soil (such as chemical precipitation, membrane filtration, adsorption, ion exchange and electro dialysis), adsorption has proved to be the most effective and economical due to its simplicity, ease of operation and low cost.

Hydrated manganese dioxide with a layered structure (birnessite) is well known as an efficient material for the selective removal of Cd ions through inner sphere complexation. However, birnessite is usually synthesized in the form of ultra-fine particles. The low hydromechanical stability of as-synthesized birnessite and its tendency to agglomerate limit its practical application. The synthesis of composite materials with manganese dioxide nanoparticles has made it possible to overcome the above-mentioned drawbacks.

The paper presents the results of the synthesis of a composite adsorbent for the selective removal of Cd ions based on clinoptilolite tuff from the Sokyrnytsia deposit (Ukraine) loaded with manganese dioxide nanoparticles. The successful synthesis of the nanocomposite adsorbent was confirmed by X-ray diffraction, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, Scanning electron microscopy and Zeta potential techniques. Samples of natural and composite clinoptilolite tuff were tested for selective removal of Cd ions from model solutions with high content of competing ions and contaminated soil (Avilés, Spain). The results obtained from the batch mode adsorption studies of Cd ions fitted well with the Langmuir isotherm, and monolayer adsorption capacity of the manganese dioxide-loaded zeolite was about 18 mg/g. The kinetic studies showed that the adsorption of Cd followed the pseudo-second-order kinetic model, which testifies to a chemisorption process. The synthesized nanocomposite adsorbent based on manganese dioxide-loaded zeolite exhibited chemical stability and high efficiency in removing Cd ions from contaminated soil, indicating its great potential for soil remediation.

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